

**BIOBLOCKS:
CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL
MADE FROM WOOD
FIBREBOARD DUST**

OVERVIEW

Bioblocks are modular construction units made from fibreboard dust, a by-product from sanding and routing fibreboards before their use in interior fittings. The dust is bound with a fully bio-based adhesive (citric acid and sorbitol). Hence, Bioblocks valorise secondary raw material that would otherwise be burnt for energy recovery and offer a circular building material for the construction sector. The current second-generation “BB II” design integrates axial voids that reduce weight and allow for reinforcement or service conduits. Male-female interlocking alignment keys enable precise mortar-free assembly, simplifying installation and supporting industrial scalability.

APPLICATIONS

Originally designed for non-load-bearing interior partitions, Bioblocks are undergoing testing and optimisation that indicate potential for structural applications. Their strength, modular design, relatively low weight (450Kg/m³), and easy handling make them a promising and cost-effective option for lightweight extension solutions. This includes the possible addition of one or two storeys of existing residential or small commercial buildings.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Lab results of the EcoReFibre Project Demonstration E: Bioblocks proved ready for pilot and industrial trials as biobased, recyclable, high performance building material.

REUSE OF WOOD DUST INTO BIOCOMPOSITES

The Bioblock concept has advanced from small lab prototypes to full-scale building blocks. The production process was optimised using a design of experiments approach (DoE). At pilot scale, Bioblocks were produced using blends of post-consumer fibreboard fine particles and dust processed by Dieffenbacher and Smartpanel production residues, with post-consumer content of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%. Performance tests achieved strong compressive strength, moisture-resistance (minimal swelling after water exposure), and promising thermal and acoustic performance. In addition, the material can be reused or recycled into new blocks multiple times, supporting circular use.

Studies indicate that Bioblocks could help improve the environmental performance of fibreboard waste and replace more harmful construction materials. However, the influence of residual synthetic resins from medium-density fibreboard (MDF) on the production process and final performance still requires further assessment.

On the way towards industrial-scale production, Smartpanel has developed a bulk processing curing method in a large container dryer.

ONGOING R&D

Smartpanel and NIBIO are optimising the product and curing system to complete the demo phase and prepare for pilot-scale production. Interlocking connection strength is being investigated, with vertical reinforcement poles across the voids and other reversible bonding systems. Upcoming tests will assess fire resistance, thermal and acoustic performance, and VOC emissions. Cost-efficiency will improve through scale-up, while wall prototypes, adhesive system assessment, and long term-monitoring will help further optimise the product and large-scale testing.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based and carbon storing material wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating wood-based materials into production helps close material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. By producing Bioblocks even MDF dust is given new life. Instead of being used for energy recovery, it is transformed into an innovative construction material.

With their modular and material reuse concept, Bioblocks support both new builds and renovations, responding to the growing demand for circular building solutions. This approach fully reflects the cascade use principle, ensuring that every fraction of wood is used to its highest potential, strengthening the circular value chain.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

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